

A Flexible Software Defined Radio Platform for Es'hail 2 Satellite Amateur Communications

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Abstract—This paper presents the project and implementation of a software defined radio (SDR) to be used primarily as part of a ground station transceiver for the geostationary Es'hail 2 satellite. The SDR contains an intermediate frequency frontend, a signal domain conversion block, and a digital signal processing stage, comprising highly reconfigurable devices: a field programmed gate array, a microcontroller unit with dedicated digital signal processing instructions, and an audio code/decode block. The SDR operates with radiofrequency signals centered, at least, between 100 MHz and 900 MHz, presents a receiver noise figure below 4 dB and can transmit signals with a maximum power higher than 10 dBm. Due to the digital signal processing stage, the SDR can deal with several different types of modulations. Besides that, the SDR can be operated by a personal computer (via universal serial bus), or work standalone.

I. INTRODUCTION

Communications satellites are, nowadays, widely used for television, telephone, internet, and military applications, among others. In the past, the geostationary orbit (GEO) satellites were reserved exclusively for commercial, military and weather forecasting applications, while satellites for amateur use and experimentation applications were placed mostly in low earth orbits (LEO) (e.g., CubeSats), and sometimes in highly elliptical orbits (HEO) (e.g., AO-10, AO-40).

As of February 2019, when the amateur transponders on board the Es'hail 2 satellite started operating [1], that amateur radio operators began to have access to a GEO satellite. The satellite payload for amateur use consists of two purposely built transponders, designated by QO-100, one for narrowband applications and the other for wideband ones.

The Es'hail 2 satellite sits at a longitude of 26° East and covers about one third of the Earth's surface, from Brazil to Thailand, as can be seen in Fig. 1. Its two QO-100 transponders are the first ever amateur radio payload placed inside a geosynchronous orbit satellite [1], allowing for a large diversity of experiments and applications fields, with a high coverage area and availability, which would not be possible without its existence. For the user, the geosynchronous orbit of the Es'hail 2 makes the access to satellite communications easier, since it is not necessary to track its trajectory as it passes over the horizon to transmit and receive radio signals to and from the satellite, as it is in the cases of LEO, medium earth orbit (MEO) and HEO satellites.

In Fig. 2 the frequency band plan of the narrowband (NB) QO-100 transponder is shown [1]. The NB transponder of QO-100 has a total bandwidth of 500 kHz (formerly 250 kHz), delimited by two continuous wave (CW) beacons, both transmitted by Radio Amateur Satellite Corporation (AMSAT) from the ground. In this transponder, each individual channel,

Fig. 1. QO-100 coverage area [1].

Fig. 2. QO-100 NB bandplan [1].

allocated to a particular user, should use no more than 2.7 kHz of bandwidth, regardless of the used modulation technique (e.g., single side band (SSB), slow scan television (SSTV)). On the other hand, the wideband (WB) transponder has a total bandwidth of 8 MHz, where the lower end spectral range of 1.5 MHz is reserved for the AMSAT DVB-S2 beacon. This beacon can be used to align the ground station's satellite dish antenna. The remaining 6.5 MHz of bandwidth are fully available to users [1].

A ground station for the Es'hail 2 QO-100 transponders can have several different implementations. One possible topology is the one shown in the simplified block diagram of Fig. 3. As illustrated, the ground station is constituted by two main functional blocks: the radiofrequency (RF) frontend (RFFE) and the software defined radio (SDR). The signal central frequencies are also given in Fig. 3.

The RFFE is responsible for the up- and down-conversion of the intermediate frequency (IF) and RF signals from and to the SDR, respectively. The RFFE is critical to the overall performance of the ground station. In the transmit path, it must transmit signals with high power (e.g., 10 W @ 2.4 GHz for the NB applications) without introducing excessive distortion, and, in the receive path, the noise added by the RFFE is of paramount importance to the attainable sensitivity of the ground station. Since the receiving frequency (downlink) is on X-band (10.489 GHz), a downconverter is needed, which

Fig. 3. QO-100 ground station simplified block diagram.

shifts the signal frequency to one belonging to the passband of the SDR receiver. On the transmitting side, it is easier to find devices/equipment that can directly output a signal at the uplink frequency (2.4 GHz), obviating the need for an up-converter. However, there are benefits in using one. For example, if the RFFE is far away from the transmitter, the signal attenuation introduced by coaxial cables can be reduced using a lower IF. In this case, the signal is only up-converted to the uplink frequency just before the power amplifier, as close as possible to the transmitting antenna.

The SDR block shown in Fig. 3 is crucial to the flexibility and adaptability of the ground station. Since the operations of this type of radios are software supported, it is relatively simple to change the IF frequencies, TX IF power, and, mainly, the type of modulation/demodulation used. All these changes are performed at software/firmware level, without requiring any change of the electronic circuits and the printed circuit board (PCB), i.e., the hardware. In this way, the ground station can support very different bit rates and modulate/demodulate signals with, for example, SSB, M-ary amplitude and phase shift keying (APSK), FSK, among others.

This paper presents a flexible software defined radio that can be used to transmit and receive IF signals to and from the RFFE of a ground station for the Es'hail 2 satellite. Despite the usage of the SDR in this particular application, it can be used in many other applications thanks to the highly programmable and configurable digital devices present in its architecture.

This paper is organized as follows: In Section II the overall architecture of the SDR is described, including component selection. Section III presents a detailed description of the most relevant digital signal processing blocks. Results are given in Section IV, followed by conclusions in Section V.

II. SDR ARCHITECTURE

In this section, the developed SDR is described in detail. To make the SDR useful for applications other than just to transmit and receive signals to and from the QO-100 Es'hail 2 satellite, its technical specifications were broadened beyond the required for the satellite ground station. Therefore, the development of the SDR started with the following initial specifications: the SDR receiver must cover at least a frequency band from 100 MHz to 900 MHz with a noise figure lower than 4 dB, and must accept a maximum input power of 0 dBm; the transmitter must cover the same frequency band, and the maximum output power must be at least 10 dBm; and the SDR must be able to work both standalone and connected to a personal computer (PC), via universal serial

bus (USB). The developed SDR is illustrated in the block diagram of Fig. 4 and its PCB is shown in Fig. 5. It should be noted that, besides the representation of the major blocks, this figure also shows their internal constitution. As can be seen, the SDR comprises a frequency conversion block (IF receiver and IF transmitter), a signal domain conversion stage, where the digital-to-analog and analog-to-digital operations are performed, a digital signal processing unit, which includes a quadrature digital down-converter (QDDC) and quadrature digital up-converter (QDUC), both implemented (Verilog) in the same field programmable gate array (FPGA), a digital signal processing microcontroller (DSP MCU) and an audio code/decode (CODEC) stage, both used, for example, to process the signal when the SDR is to be operated standalone. Despite only detailing the most relevant blocks, the SDR also contains dedicated blocks for clock generation (synchronization), power supply and management and system monitoring and control. The SDR interfaces directly with the RF frontend equipment, the user (e.g., microphone and headphones) and/or with the user's personal computer through a USB connection.

A. Frequency conversion stage

As illustrated in Fig. 4, the IF receiver is based on the superheterodyne topology. The receiver was implemented with an integrated circuit (IC), the Rafael Micro R820T2, which is found in many USB digital video broadcasting - terrestrial (DVB-T) tuner dongles [2]. This IC integrates a low noise amplifier (LNA), an RF tunable filter, a synthesized local oscillator (LO), a frequency mixer, an IF filter and a variable gain amplifier (VGA). All its internal functional blocks are very flexible and digitally configurable through an Inter-Integrated Circuit (I²C) interface. The IC can receive signals from 42 to 1002 MHz and has a low noise figure of 3.5 dB, an image rejection higher than 65 dBc, a gain control of 104 dB and allows an absolute maximum input signal power of 10 dBm. The signal output can occupy a frequency band between 500 kHz and about 10 MHz. All these characteristics are relevant to the performance of the SDR receiver and fulfill all the required specifications.

The main function of the IF transmitter is to shift the central frequency of the output signal (in-phase and quadrature) of the signal domain conversion block to the desired IF frequency and the amplification of that signal before its transmission. As depicted in Fig. 4, the signal up-conversion is handled by the Analog Devices ADL5385 quadrature mixer. The output signal frequency of the mixer can go up to 2.2 GHz, only requiring a single-ended LO signal, since, internally, it derives a 90-degree phase-shifted version for the quadrature arm. This process, however, requires that the input LO frequency be twice that of the desired RF carrier frequency. As such, the LO is generated by the Analog Devices ADF4351 synthesizer, which can reach a frequency of 4.4 GHz. At the output of the IF transmitter, the signal is amplified by the Analog Devices ADL5610 amplifier, which presents an operating frequency range from 30 MHz to 6 GHz and a maximum signal power of 20.4 dBm at 900 MHz. Therefore, the IF transmitter is capable of operating with signals with frequencies between 100 MHz to 900 MHz and powers up to 10 dBm, as desired initially.

Fig. 4. SDR block diagram.

Fig. 5. SDR assembled PCB.

B. Signal domain conversion stage

After down-conversion, the signal is digitized by the LTC2205 analog-to-digital converter (ADC) IC, from Analog Devices, and fed into the FPGA for processing, as illustrated in Fig. 4. The LTC2205 ADC is a 16-bit ADC capable of sampling signals at up to 65 Msps and has a high spurious-free dynamic range (SFDR). On the other hand, in the transmission path, the baseband in-phase (I) and quadrature (Q) signals from the FPGA are converted to the analog domain through an Analog Devices AD9117 14-bit digital-to-analog converter (DAC), which operates at up to 125 Msps, low-pass filtered and fed into the IF transmitter, as shown in Fig. 4.

C. Digital signal processing stage

The digital signal processing unit comprehends an FPGA, a DSP and an audio CODEC, as illustrated in Fig. 4. The audio CODEC, a TSC25 from Tempo Semiconductor, is only used to encode analog audio signals to a digital data stream or to decode the received data stream to analog audio, although it can be programmed to perform various audio processing effects (e.g., compression, equalization, DC removal).

1) *FPGA*: The FPGA used in the SDR is the iCE40HX8K, from Lattice Semiconductor. It is the largest device of the family, with 7680 logic cells, 128 kb of block random access memory (BRAM) and two phase-locked loop (PLL) intellectual property (IP) blocks. This choice is primarily based on the fact that it is the first FPGA family to have an open-source toolchain available [3]. The bitstream is loaded into the FPGA by the system management microcontroller unit (MCU) via a serial peripheral interface (SPI).

In the receive path (QDDC block), as illustrated in Fig. 4, samples from the ADC arrive at the FPGA through a 16-bit parallel bus. There is a small BRAM buffer that can capture a window of samples directly from the ADC, which can then be read by the system management MCU, for analysis. To obtain the data from the received samples, first, it is necessary to convert them to baseband, obtaining a complex IQ signal, since the received samples are from the IF receiver output signal. To achieve this, the sampled signal (in the digital domain) is mixed with a sine and cosine tones produced by a numerically controlled oscillator (NCO). Following the numerical mixers, both signal components (I and Q) are down-sampled by cascaded integrator-comb (CIC) filters to ensure the data can be processed in time by the DSP. After decimation, the I and Q samples are sent from the FPGA to the DSP via an inter-IC sound (I^2S) interface. This interface, although originally created for carrying audio samples, is very convenient for transporting IQ (complex) data, since one can easily map the real and imaginary parts of a sample as the left and right channels of an audio stream.

In the transmit path (QDUC block), the IQ data to be transmitted, which arrives through the previously mentioned I^2S interface, is first up-sampled to one fourth of the DAC sampling rate, using the same CIC filter topology as in the QDDC, as shown in Fig. 4. After the first interpolation stage, there is a quadrature mixer that allows up-conversion of the digital baseband into a digital IF. This numerical mixer allows the use of the transmitter as a heterodyne transmitter. This numerical mixer is, however, optional, since it is possible to bypass the numerical up-conversion stage. Following the mixer, the signal is up-sampled again, to match the final DAC sample rate, and clocked out of the FPGA on a double data rate (DDR) 14-bit parallel bus.

To control and obtain the status information of all the logic blocks inside the FPGA, there is a register page accessible via SPI. There is also an interrupt controller which can multiplex various internal signals into an interrupt line for the system management and DSP MCUs to respond to.

2) *DSP*: An Atmel SAM V71 microcontroller was used as a DSP. The part contains an ARM Cortex-M7 core clocked at 300 MHz, as well as instruction and data caches. It features 2 MB of flash memory, 384 kB of SRAM, and supports double-precision floating point instructions, as well as ARM's single instruction multiple data (SIMD) DSP instructions, which boost the speed of digital signal processing algorithms.

Fig. 6. Pipelined complex mixer timing diagram

D. Clock generator

To generate the various clock signals needed for the different blocks, the Silicon Labs Si5351C I²C programmable frequency synthesizer was used. This is a very flexible IC that can generate non-integer related clock frequencies at each of its outputs, bringing even more flexibility to the design. Four dedicated clock signals are routed to global buffer inputs of the FPGA, and one clock signal is routed to the DSP microcontroller. Additionally, the system management MCU can also be clocked from this synthesizer.

III. DIGITAL PROCESSING BLOCKS IMPLEMENTATION

A. FPGA

As stated before, it is in the FPGA that the digital up- and down-converters (Fig. 4) are implemented. The main functional blocks used to perform that conversion operations are the mixers, oscillators and interpolation/decimation filters, all of which are described next.

1) *Mixer*: To mix two signals, it is necessary to compute the product of one by the other. Multiplications are one of the most resource intensive operations in an FPGA [4], therefore, sometimes manufacturers opt to include IP specific circuits designed exclusively for this purpose. Unfortunately, the iCE40HX8K FPGA, used here, does not include any dedicated multiplication circuit IP. This poses a design challenge that is aggravated when the number of real multiplication operations needed for a complex product is considered, as is the case for IQ data, as illustrated in Eq. 1:

$$(a + bi)(c + di) = (ac - bd) + (ad + bc)i \quad (1)$$

where i is the imaginary unit and a, b, c and d are real numbers. Eq. 1 shows that four multiplications and two additions are required to multiply two complex I and Q signals (samples), as used in the QDUC (see Fig. 4). Instead of instantiating four different multipliers, a compromise can be made between latency and FPGA resource usage by using only one instance and pipelining the multiplication process [5]. The process is controlled by a finite state machine (FSM), which, ideally,

requires four clock cycles to complete the multiplication of two complex numbers. Therefore, performing four sequential multiplications using only one multiplier instance, inherently means that the maximum sampling rate that the multiplier can process is one fourth of its clock speed. However, due to the additional operations required by fixed-point multiplication (result rounding and saturation) and data synchronization, the total latency is increased to ten clock cycles, as illustrated by the timing diagram represented in Fig. 6. As can be seen, all states ('b00', 'b01', 'b10' and 'b11') of the FSM are identical in that they all load two numbers (factors) into the multiplier and retrieve the multiplication result (product). However, state 'b11' is also responsible for loading the next input data (Input I/Q and LO I/Q) into their corresponding buffering registers). This allows the input data to change while the multiplication takes place as long as the four inputs are valid when they are loaded into the buffering registers. State 'b00' is where the final result is moved into the output registers, as can be seen in the complete pipeline depicted in Fig. 6.

The mixer used in the receiving chain is similar to the full complex IQ mixer just described. The main difference lies in the fact that it only requires two multiplications, because, although the LO is still complex (I/Q), the input data is real.

2) *NCO*: The numerical local oscillator signals used in the digital transmitter and receiver mixers for the digital up- and down-conversion, respectively, are generated by two numerically controlled oscillators. An NCO is a digital signal generator that produces a discrete sinusoidal waveform, in this case, complex-valued.

The NCO architecture used in the two developed NCOs is shown in Fig. 7. The 31-bit frequency control word is integrated by the phase accumulator. The output of the accumulator is then truncated to a 11-bit phase word that indexes a look-up table (LUT) containing the amplitude information of a sine wave. In this case, a 90° shifted phase word is also used to index the LUT to generate a cosine wave. The discretized combined sine and cosine waves represent the complex-valued LO signal. Optionally, a noise shaping stage can be inserted before the truncation of the frequency word.

Fig. 7. NCO architecture.

This noise shaping helps to reduce the non-harmonic spurious products introduced by the truncation (quantization) process [6]. In this implementation, noise shaping is achieved by storing the quantization error and adding it to the next sample, as given in Eq. 2:

$$\begin{cases} y[n] = x[n] + e[n - 1] \\ e[n] = y_{\text{quantized}}[n] - y[n] \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $x[n]$ is the output of the phase accumulator, $y[n]$ is the phase word before truncation, $y_{\text{quantized}}[n]$ is the quantized phase word and $e[n]$ is the quantization error introduced at sample n . This negative feedback loop acts as a low pass filter which helps reduce the power of the spurious tones at higher frequencies.

The frequency of the NCO depicted in Fig. 7 can be given by Eq. 3:

$$f_{\text{out}} = f_{\text{clk}} \frac{\Delta_F}{2^N} \quad (3)$$

where Δ_F is the value of the frequency tuning word (FTW), N is the bit length of the FTW and f_{clk} is the frequency at which the phase accumulator is clocked. Note that the resolution frequency of the NCO is given by $f_{\text{res}} = \frac{f_{\text{clk}}}{2^N}$. The adjust or tuning of the NCO frequency is performed by changing the FTW value [7]. Considering $N = 31$ and a clock frequency of 49.152 MHz (value used in the SDR demonstration application), the NCO achieves a frequency resolution of $f_{\text{res}} = 0.023$ Hz.

Since a sine wave can be split into four quadrants, and the function value at each quadrant is the same, albeit inverted in time or symmetrical in amplitude, it is only necessary to store one fourth of the amplitude representation of the function, thereby reducing BRAM usage. In this application, the LUTs consist of 512 words, 16-bit each, making for a total BRAM usage of 8 Kb per LUT.

3) *CIC Filter*: Given that there are very different sampling rates involved in the SDR, the need for up- and down-sampling signals in an efficient manner arises. Since any sample rate conversion is likely to produce aliasing, there is always some kind of filtering involved, either before (when down-sampling) or after the conversion (when up-sampling) [8]. There are several types of digital filters that can be used for this task, however, one that stands out by its simplicity, low resource usage and computational efficiency, is the CIC filter [9], also commonly referred to as a Sinc filter, due to the shape of its frequency response [10]. A CIC filter is composed only by sum and subtraction operations, having a sample rate converter built into its architecture, as can be seen in Fig. 8.

In Fig. 9, the typical frequency response of a decimating CIC filter for a rate change of 8 ($R = 8$) is represented, along-

Fig. 8. CIC architecture: a) decimator, b) interpolator.

Fig. 9. Visualization of the spectral folding in a CIC filter: (a) before decimation; (b) after $R = 8$ decimation [10].

Fig. 10. CIC filter response for different numbers of integrator/comb stages ($R = 8$).

side a visual representation of the spectral folding that occurs after decimation. By modifying the number of integrator and comb stages (M), the attenuation of the aliased components that will fold onto the passband can be changed [10], as illustrated in Fig. 10.

The implementation allows the configuration of the number of stages (M) and of the input and output word sizes. The relationship between the number of stages and the integrator word size is given by $N = M \log_2(R)$, where N is the internal word size, M is the number of integrator and comb stages and R is the sample rate change. Internally, all operations are performed on N -bit words. The input samples are sign-

extended into N -bit words at the start, and the last stage's output is truncated to match the requested output word size.

B. DSP

For the QO-100 satellite application, an SSB modulator and demodulator (MODEM), described by [11], was implemented in the DSP MCU. The block diagram of the SSB MODEM is depicted in Fig. 4. A small library of DSP functions was produced, which contains implementations of commonly used algorithms, such as automatic gain control (AGC), oscillators and AM/FM demodulators. A finite impulse response (FIR) filter library was also developed, supporting regular, sparse, decimating and interpolating topologies, both for real and complex valued signals. All algorithms are accelerated, where possible, by taking advantage of the SIMD DSP instructions.

1) *SSB Modulator*: The audio samples from the audio CODEC are first band-pass filtered to restrict the signal to the aforementioned 2.7 kHz channel bandwidth limit, as illustrated in Fig. 4. Afterwards, a pre-emphasis filter is applied, in order to improve the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) for the entire frequency range [12]. The digitized audio signal, after its peak is levelled by the AGC, is now passed through a FIR filter that approximates the Hilbert transform, in order to generate a complex-valued signal [13]. Since this filter introduces a delay equal to half the number of taps, N , it is necessary to also delay the real component by this amount, in order to keep synchronized both the I and Q components. The I/Q signal is then up-sampled and filtered by a final low-pass FIR filter, and loaded onto the direct memory access (DMA) buffer for I²S transmission to the QDUC.

2) *SSB Demodulator*: The SSB demodulator is basically a reversed copy of the modulator. Samples from the QDDC are filtered, downsampled, and the Q component is passed through the same Hilbert transform FIR, while the I component is delayed. Afterwards, they are summed (or subtracted) in order to produce a real-valued audio signal from the upper (or lower) sideband. This audio signal is de-emphasized by the output FIR filter and passed through an AGC block, before being routed to the audio CODEC. The AGC is used here to ensure that the output signal peak value is always maintained at the desired level.

IV. RESULTS

The timing analysis tools show that the critical path delay of the FPGA design is 14.52 ns, which yields a theoretical maximum clock frequency of 68.87 MHz. The design utilizes 7288 of the 7680 available logic cells (94%), 100 kb of BRAM (78%) and 73 I/O lines (28%). The DSP can keep up with the processing required for the currently implemented SSB MODEM, as it takes approximately 2 ms to perform all the calculations on a buffer of samples, and sits idle for 3 ms before the next block is received. Tests also show that the device can safely run at 360 MHz, instead of the rated clock of 300 MHz, which should result in about a 20% improvement in the number of instructions executed per second. The firmware for the DSP uses 35.34 kB of the available 2 MB of flash memory, and 151.85 kB of the available 384 kB of RAM.

After confirming, in the laboratory, that the SDR was operating accordingly with the specifications, real experimental

tests were performed. To that end, the SDR was connected to an RF frontend, and a half-duplex voice communication was successfully accomplished. During the real environment assessment of the SDR (and satellite ground station), the signal spectrum and its central frequency was always tracked and monitored in the QO-100 narrowband WebSDR [14].

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the development and implementation of an SDR, whose main application is in a Es'hail 2 satellite ground station. The detailed block diagram of the SDR is presented, showing that it comprises an intermediate frontend, a signal domain conversion block, and a digital signal processing unit. The flexibility, adaptability, and versatility of the SDR are guaranteed by the programmable devices (FPGA, MCU DSP and audio CODEC) used in it. All the used circuits/blocks were detailed, and the implementation of the main digital functional blocks was described and explained. Operations in the digital domain, such as decimation, interpolation, filtering, mixing, LO generation, among others, were also described. The developed SDR can work connected, via USB, to a PC, or standalone, and can deal with different types of signal modulations. Experimental tests shown that the SDR can receive/transmit radiofrequency signals located between 100 MHz and 900 MHz, and real world tests confirmed that the SDR, when integrated in the ground station, can successfully transmit and receive signals to and from the Es'hail 2 satellite.

REFERENCES

- [1] Peter Gülzow (DB2OS), *P4-A / Es'hail 2 / Qatar-OSCAR 100*, 2019, https://www.uska.ch/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/F3_db2os-qo-100-der-erste-geostationaere-oscar.pdf
- [2] *About RTL-SDR*, <https://www.rtl-sdr.com/about-rtl-sdr/>
- [3] Claire Wolf, *Project IceStorm*, 2015, <https://clifford.at/icestorm>
- [4] Ferry Wahyu Wibowo, *Comparison of Multiplication Algorithms Based on FPGA*, 2nd Borneo International Conference on Applied Mathematics and Engineering (BICAME), 2018
- [5] A. Panato, S. Silva, F. Wagner, M. Johann, R. Reis, S. Bampi, *Design of very deep pipelined multipliers for FPGAs*, Design, Automation and Test in Europe Conference and Exhibition, February 2004
- [6] G.A. Zimmerman, M.J. Flanagan, *Spur-reduced numerically-controlled oscillator for digital receivers*, Twenty-Sixth Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems & Computers, October 1992
- [7] Don Hummels, *Numerically Controlled Oscillators*, https://web.eece.maine.edu/~hummels/classes/ece486/docs/NCO_tutorial.pdf
- [8] Faheem Sheikh, Shahid Masud, *Sample rate conversion filter design for multi-standard software radios*, Digital Signal Processing, vol. 20, issue 1, pages 3-12, January 2010
- [9] E. Hogenauer, *An economical class of digital filters for decimation and interpolation*, IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing, vol. 92, issue 2, April 1981
- [10] Rick Lyons, *A Beginner's Guide To Cascaded Integrator-Comb (CIC) Filters*, March 20, 2020, <https://www.dsprelated.com/showarticle/1337.php>
- [11] Chang Yu-Hsien, *Single Sideband modulation*, 2012, <https://ses.library.usyd.edu.au/bitstream/handle/2123/8252/Single%20Side-Band%20Modulator%20.pdf;jsessionid=C54776616A74EB35C3F364D2E69B4CD0?sequence=2>
- [12] R. Vergin, D. O'Shaughnessy, *Pre-Emphasis and Speech Recognition*, Canadian Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering, September 1995
- [13] Yi-Wen Liu, *Hilbert Transform and Applications*, in Fourier Transform Applications, London, United Kingdom: IntechOpen April 2012
- [14] *Qatar-OSCAR 100 Narrowband WebSDR*, <https://eshail.batc.org.uk/nb/>